

ABSTRACT

Investigating the Relevance of Genetic Variation at Post-Translational Modification Sites in the Polygenic Risk Model for Alzheimer's disease-associated Phenotypes

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Alzheimer's Disease (AD) is a debilitating neurological condition primarily affecting the elderly, with recent reports indicating that genetic variation contributes to 70% of AD cases. The pathology and progression of the disease are categorized into early-onset (EOAD) with sporadic or autosomal dominant familial causes, and late-onset prevalent (LOAD) with polygenic origins. Studies, including inheritance-based research and genome-wide association studies (GWAS), have identified various components, highlighting the complex polygenic nature of this condition. These investigations pave the way for discovering crucial biomarkers for early diagnosis and potential therapeutic strategies. While large-scale GWAS have identified numerous risk loci, interpreting functional implications, such as effect size and cellular impact of genetic variations, remains a challenge. To address this, our project focuses on annotating genomic sites encoding amino acid residues subject to post-translational modifications (PTMs) to distinguish between neutral variant effects and those influencing the phenotype. We hypothesize that these modifications significantly contribute to disease risk, given their association with key genes in the monogenic form of Alzheimer's Disease (EOAD), including APP, PSEN1, PSEN2, and MAPT. These PTMs induce changes in critical pathways underlying the disease's pathology. Our proposal involves creating a gene annotation database from GWAS studies encompassing both polygenic and monogenic forms, facilitating the investigation of genetic variation effects on potential PTM target sites in risk prediction. Additionally, leveraging the SABE ABraOM genomic variant repository from Brazilian individuals will provide insights into a mixed population and analyze the impact of various local ancestries on Alzheimer's Disease risk. The application, adaptation, and enhancement of bioinformatics tools for assessing AD manifestation risk represent a significant contribution to public health. Preliminary results indicate a modest contribution of post-translational modifications (PTMs) to Alzheimer's prediction, with acetylation modifications emerging as particularly relevant. Furthermore, Polygenic Risk Score (PRS) models applied to Kunkle and Bellenguez datasets have demonstrated improved performance in identifying Early-Onset Alzheimer's Disease (EOAD) cases, highlighting the crucial role of including APOE 4 allele-related information for identifying Late-Onset Alzheimer's Disease (LOAD) cases.

Keywords: Genome-wide Association Studies (GWAS); Polygenic Risk Score (PRS); Admixed Population.

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